

Table S2. Body mass index

Table with columns: SNP*, Chr, Pos, Effect allele, Other allele, EAF, BMI GWAS (Beta, SE, P-value), Breast cancer-specific: All (Beta, SE, P-value), Breast cancer-specific: ER-positive (Beta, SE, P-value), Breast cancer-specific: ER-negative (Beta, SE, P-value). Rows include SNPs such as rs543874, rs4715210, rs7647305, etc.

* Total number of SNPs after harmonization and filtering from originally 287 SNPs

SNPs removed: Overlapping between BMI and T2DM
SNPs removed: In linkage disequilibrium with SNPs in T2DM

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
Chr: Chromosome
Pos: Position
EAF: Effect Allele Frequency
SE: Standard Error

Table S3. Height

Table with columns for SNP, Chr, Pos, Effect allele, Other allele, EAF, Height GWAS (Beta, SE, P-value), Breast cancer-specific: All (Beta, SE, P-value), Breast cancer-specific: ER-positive (Beta, SE, P-value), and Breast cancer-specific: ER-negative (Beta, SE, P-value). It contains 194 rows of genomic data.

* Total number of SNPs after harmonization and filtering from originally 173 SNPs

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
Chr: Chromosome
Pos: Position
EAF: Effect Allele Frequency
SE: Standard Error

Table S4. Mammographic density

SNP*	Chr	Pos	Effect allele	Other allele	EAF	Mammographic density GWAS			Breast cancer-specific: All			Breast cancer-specific: ER-positive			Breast cancer-specific: ER-negative		
						Beta	SE	P-value	Beta	SE	P-value	Beta	SE	P-value	Beta	SE	P-value
rs10995190	10	64278682	A	G	0.147	-0.240	0.031	1.00E-16	-0.005	0.024	8.44E-01	0.039	0.031	2.16E-01	-0.093	0.050	6.12E-02
rs10034692	4	75419787	A	G	0.719	-0.160	0.031	2.00E-10	-0.017	0.019	3.83E-01	-0.010	0.024	6.78E-01	-0.019	0.038	6.22E-01
rs1033556	12	103011894	A	G	0.979	-0.410	0.082	4.00E-10	0.154	0.055	5.37E-03	0.097	0.071	1.70E-01	0.189	0.108	8.15E-02
rs12665607	6	151946629	A	T	0.085	-0.170	0.040	2.00E-08	0.080	0.029	6.31E-03	0.078	0.038	3.98E-02	0.037	0.057	5.11E-01
rs7289126	22	38628306	A	C	0.458	-0.110	0.020	3.00E-08	-0.022	0.017	1.97E-01	-0.018	0.022	4.19E-01	-0.065	0.034	5.79E-02

* Total number of SNPs after harmonization and filtering from originally 12 SNPs

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
 Chr: Chromosome
 Pos: Position
 EAF: Effect Allele Frequency
 SE: Standard Error

Table S7. Physical activity

SNP*	Chr	Pos	Effect allele	Other allele	EAF	Physical activity GWAS			Breast cancer-specific: All			Breast cancer-specific: ER-positive			Breast cancer-specific: ER-negative		
						Beta	SE	P-value	Beta	SE	P-value	Beta	SE	P-value	Beta	SE	P-value
rs55657917	17	43844560	T	G	0.787	-0.037	0.005	8.00E-12	-0.015	0.021	4.79E-01	-0.044	0.027	0.1028055	0.069	0.042	1.03E-01
rs59499656	18	40768309	A	T	0.655	-0.028	0.005	2.00E-09	-0.009	0.018	6.19E-01	-0.024	0.023	0.3041047	0.027	0.037	4.60E-01
rs6775319	3	18758501	A	T	0.276	0.027	0.005	4.00E-08	-0.021	0.019	2.74E-01	-0.025	0.025	0.299366	0.006	0.039	4.60E-01

* Total number of SNPs after harmonization and filtering from originally 7 SNPs

SNP: Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
 Chr: Chromosome
 Pos: Position
 EAF: Effect Allele Frequency
 SE: Standard Error

